

INTELLECTUAL OPENNESS AND ITS RELATIONSHIP TO STRATEGIC VIGILANCE AMONG PUBLIC SCHOOL PRINCIPALS IN THE SULTANATE OF OMAN

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Abstract

The present study aimed to identify the level of intellectual openness and its relationship to strategic vigilance among public school principals in the Sultanate of Oman from teachers' perspectives. The study adopted the descriptive correlational approach. A questionnaire consisting of two main domains, namely intellectual openness and strategic vigilance, was developed and administered to a random sample of 380 male and female teachers from the governorates of South Al Sharqiyah, Al Dakhiliyah, and Muscat.

The findings revealed that the level of intellectual openness among school principals was high, with an average of (4.054). The level of strategic vigilance was also high, with a mean score of (4.170). In addition, the results revealed a strong statistically significant positive correlation between intellectual openness and strategic vigilance, with an overall correlation coefficient of (0.814). The study recommended promoting a culture of intellectual openness among school leaders, integrating strategic vigilance into professional development programs, and supporting modern administrative practices based on foresight and adaptation to contemporary educational and technological changes.

Keywords: Strategic Vigilance, statistically, contemporary, steadfastness, community.

Introduction

The world in the present era is witnessing a great and rapid knowledge, information and technological revolution, which has directly affected the educational system and the methods of leadership and management in educational institutions. It has become imperative and not a luxury to adapt to dynamic environments characterized by constant change, which requires an effective leadership style that goes beyond traditional management to modern leadership styles to keep pace with the scale of rapid and significant changes. The leader is required to possess intellectual and cognitive characteristics that help him deal with new developments with flexibility and efficiency.

Al-Otaibi and Al-Hussaini (2025) point out that educational institutions still face a set of challenges, most notably the increasing number of students, the diversity of their needs, and the pressures of administrative work on teachers and administrators. These challenges necessitate the existence of effective methods and strategies, led by school principals, aimed at raising the level of their educational performance in a way that ensures the achievement of the goals of the educational system to be globally competitive. Muhammad (2022) explained that the school principal is primarily responsible for creating a positive organizational culture in order to achieve the strategic goals of the school that make students able to face the challenges of future life, and contribute to their cognitive, emotional and psychological growth.

Intellectual openness is one of the basic concepts in the fields of education, psychology and sociology. It refers to a flexible thinking style and is also one of the most important personality traits that reflects an individual's readiness to accept new ideas and opinions and respect different viewpoints. An intellectually open school principal is characterized by flexibility, acceptance of criticism and the ability to engage in constructive dialogue. A study by Othman (2025) from Indonesia showed that the personality of a school principal has a significant impact on improving school performance, especially one who possesses positive personal qualities such as openness and flexibility, and creates a positive school climate. Intellectual openness is a balance between steadfastness to principles and flexibility in thinking. It is an essential skill for leaders in all sectors, especially the education sector, to build a tolerant and progressive society based on dialogue and knowledge. Leaders who embrace intellectual openness are always eager to make a positive impact on their employees, their communities, and the surrounding environment. Al-Yafai et al. (2023) stated that, in light of the rapid information

revolutions of the current era, intellectual openness and intellectual security for school students are urgent necessities. All measures must be taken and implemented meticulously to protect these students from intellectual deviation and to preserve their religious, national, cultural, and social identity. Intellectual openness has several dimensions: accepting differing opinions, which entails respecting diverse viewpoints; intellectual flexibility, which is the ability to modify positions based on new information; intellectual curiosity, which is the desire for continuous learning; and critical thinking, which involves analyzing ideas and not accepting them without scrutiny.

Ramila Wasiti (2019) pointed out that intellectual skills are among the most important characteristics in the contemporary era that must be available in school principals, including intellectual openness, which contributes to their ability to understand the work and be prepared to accept new ideas and opinions. It can be said that intellectual openness helps school principals appreciate the intellectual diversity of teachers, students, parents, and the culture of the local community of the school, which contributes to organizing the work and simplifying methods and procedures to achieve the best possible performance in tasks.

One of the most prominent results of Al-Anzi's study (2023) is that the role of the school is to control intellectual openness through group dialogue, moral refinement, providing learners with modern knowledge and skills, developing values and scientific attitudes, consolidating identity, and developing educational curricula to confront the effects of openness.

Strategic vigilance is a proactive process of anticipating the future by monitoring the internal and external environment, predicting potential scenarios, and thus assisting decision-makers within the institution to make effective decisions. It can also be said that the concept of strategic vigilance is a system for collecting and analyzing information to anticipate and deal with future changes (Zaid, 2017). Strategic vigilance is defined as the institution's ability to absorb and creatively analyze new information within a framework that supports its competitive strategy with other organizations both locally and globally (Mahmoud, 2025). It is also defined as an informational and proactive system that helps the institution or organization identify opportunities and threats early, thus by enhancing its competitiveness. Strategic vigilance is considered one of the modern tools that help school administrators adapt to rapid changes. The dimensions of strategic vigilance, as explained by Al-

Mutairi (2024), are: Environmental vigilance: which is manifested in monitoring societal, educational, economic, social, cultural and legal changes that have an impact on the activity of the educational institution; Technological vigilance: which is represented in monitoring technological developments and continuous monitoring of everything related to current and future technical aspects within the framework of the educational institution; Competitive vigilance: which is comparing performance with other educational institutions, and working to understand and analyze everything related to the competing institution by obtaining and collecting information, analyzing strengths and weaknesses, then processing them to draw conclusions and use them in decision-making.

Saad and others (2025) stated that strategic vigilance is a vital tool that contributes to the development and sustainability of educational institutions to keep pace with rapid transformations, by monitoring changes and anticipating opportunities and challenges, which contributes to the ability to adapt to global changes to achieve quality education. From the above, it can be said that strategic vigilance is the analysis of changes in the internal and external environment of the institution, with the aim of anticipating opportunities and threats and making proactive decisions that support the achievement of long-term goals.

Al-Subaie's study (2025) concluded that it is necessary to integrate the approaches of strategic vigilance and smart leadership within the professional development programs for school principals, and to organize training courses to enable school management to develop innovative strategies to extract knowledge, skills and experiences from the minds of employees to deal with emerging problems and evolving circumstances.

Intellectual openness provides the school principal with mental flexibility that enables him to accept new ideas and analyze them objectively. Here, the importance of the principal's strategic vigilance becomes clear, which plays a role in making him aware of the surrounding challenges and opportunities and the ability to make proactive decisions based on an accurate reading of reality, which contributes to developing school performance and achieving the goals set in an environment characterized by rapid change.

Many studies have been conducted. In the field of intellectual openness, Owaidat (2021) conducted a study that aimed to identify the degree to which private school principals practice diversity management and its relationship to the intellectual openness of teachers from their point of view. He

used the descriptive correlational approach, applied to 243 male and female teachers, and the questionnaire was the tool for collecting data. The study concluded that the level of intellectual openness among teachers in Jordanian private schools from their point of view was at a moderate level. The results showed that there were statistically significant differences between the arithmetic means of the level of intellectual openness among teachers attributed to the gender variable and in favor of females, and to the difference in academic qualification in favor of those with postgraduate degrees.

Malouh and Abdul-Hakim (2022) conducted a study aimed at identifying the intellectual openness of public and private school principals in the Bani Obaid district in light of the Islamic school from the teachers' point of view. The study adopted the descriptive survey method, applied to 315 teachers, and the questionnaire was the tool for collecting data. The study concluded that the degree of intellectual openness of school principals in the Bani Obaid district in light of the Islamic school was high.

Al-Anzi (2023) conducted a study that aimed to identify contemporary intellectual openness and its impact on the value system from the perspective of Islamic education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The study adopted the descriptive inductive method, through extrapolation and analysis of theoretical literature and previous studies. The research concluded that the most prominent negative effects of intellectual openness on the value system are summarized in the emergence of many dissenting intellectual movements, imitation of Western civilization and fascination with their customs and traditions.

Bilge and Konakli (2024) conducted a study that aimed to examine the impact of school principals' political skills on schools' openness to change in Kocaeli Province, Turkey. The study used a descriptive approach through a scale called "Schools' Openness to Change." The study was applied to 613 teachers, and it concluded that school principals' political skills positively affect schools' openness to change.

Hilat (2024) conducted a study aimed at identifying the degree of commitment of secondary school principals in Qasaba Irbid, Jordan to intellectual openness and its relationship to their level of administrative creativity from the teachers' point of view. He used the descriptive correlational approach, and the questionnaire was the data collection tool, which was applied to 403 male and female teachers. The results of the study showed that the degree of commitment of secondary school

principals in Qasaba Irbid to intellectual openness was high.

Witthöft and Pietsch (2025) conducted a study that aimed to examine the relationship between the open innovation mindset of German school leaders and its impact on digital innovation. The study used the descriptive survey method, and the questionnaire was the data collection tool, applied to 411 principals. The results of the study showed that school leaders have an open innovation mindset and promote a collaborative culture.

Many previous studies have been conducted in the field of strategic vigilance, as Saleh (2023) conducted a study that aimed to develop the performance of the principals of technical secondary schools in Minya Governorate in light of the strategic vigilance approach. The study used the descriptive method, and it was applied to 760 male and female teachers, and the questionnaire was the tool for collecting data. The results concluded that the level of performance of the principals of secondary schools in Minya Governorate in strategic vigilance was average.

Al-Kindi (2023) conducted a study aimed at identifying the degree of availability of strategic mindfulness dimensions among school principals in the Al Ain Educational Zone in the United Arab Emirates. The study adopted the descriptive approach, and the questionnaire was the data collection tool, which was applied to 35 principals. The results showed that the degree of availability of strategic mindfulness dimensions among school principals in the Al Ain Educational Zone in the United Arab Emirates was moderate.

While Lubna and Rateb's study (2024) aimed to identify the reality of strategic vigilance practice among school principals from the perspective of secondary school teachers and the principals themselves in Palestine, the study adopted the descriptive analytical approach, and the questionnaire was the data collection tool, which was applied to 221 principals and teachers, and the results showed that the reality of strategic vigilance practice among principals from the perspective of secondary school teachers and principals in Palestine is high.

Al-Subaie (2025) conducted a study aimed at determining the level of strategic vigilance among the principals of public secondary schools in Taif Governorate. The research used the descriptive method, and the questionnaire was the tool for collecting data, which was applied to 299 teachers. The research concluded that the level of strategic

vigilance among the principals of public secondary schools in Taif Governorate was moderate.

As is evident from the above, there are aspects of agreement and disagreement. The current study agreed with previous studies in adopting the descriptive correlational approach to the study, except for the study of Malouh and Abdul-Hakim (2022) and the study of Witthöft and Pietsch (2025), which used the descriptive survey approach. Al-Anzi's study (2023) used the descriptive inductive approach. The current study differed in its treatment of the topic of intellectual openness and its relationship to strategic vigilance among public school principals in three governorates (South Al Sharqiyah, Al Dakhiliyah, and Muscat) in the Sultanate of Oman, and in its treatment of intellectual openness as an independent variable and strategic vigilance as a dependent variable. The current study differed in the time and place limits from previous studies, and the current study differed in its treatment of the sample, which consisted of teachers, except for the study of Lubna and Rateb (2024), whose study sample consisted of principals and teachers.

Based on the importance of intellectual traits in enhancing leadership performance and the scarcity of studies on this topic - to the best of the researcher's knowledge - this encouraged him to conduct such a study to determine the degree of practice of intellectual openness and the reality of the level of strategic vigilance among public school principals in the Sultanate of Oman.

Problem Statement

The effective school in the 21st century is an educational institution responsible for nurturing students and influencing their intellectual, social, and psychological development, preparing them to adapt to contemporary life. Scientific and technological advancements have contributed to the emergence of ideas, practices, and customs that were not present in our societies. This necessitates that school administrators face increasing challenges in these modern developments, requiring them to engage with diverse ideas and practices to identify strengths, weaknesses, and potential threats. (Ajouj, 2024)

In light of the recommendations of several studies, such as Hilat's (2024), which emphasized the importance of school principals holding meetings with teachers and students to address misleading ideas and avoid being swayed by other cultures, and Al-Barazi and Mubarak's (2024) recommendation to form specialized, innovative teams of qualified

individuals to train specialists in the field of strategic vigilance, this study was conducted.

Through his experience as a teacher, the researcher observed a disparity in the practice of intellectual openness among public school principals. Some exhibit intellectual rigidity and closed-mindedness with teachers, students, and parents, while others demonstrate intellectual openness. This disparity may impact their strategic vigilance. Therefore, this study aims to identify the degree of intellectual openness practiced and its relationship to strategic vigilance among public school principals in the Sultanate of Oman, from the perspective of teachers.

Research Questions

This study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of intellectual openness practiced by public school principals in the Sultanate of Oman from the teachers' perspective?
2. What is the level of strategic vigilance among public school principals in the Sultanate of Oman from the teachers' perspective?
3. Is there a statistically significant correlation ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the level of intellectual openness practiced by public school principals in the Sultanate of Oman and their level of strategic vigilance ?

Study Objectives

The current study aims to achieve the following:

1. To identify the level of intellectual openness practiced by public school principals in the Sultanate of Oman from the teachers' perspective.
2. To identify the level of strategic vigilance among public school principals in the Sultanate of Oman from the teachers' perspective.
3. To identify the correlation between the level of intellectual openness of public school principals in the Sultanate of Oman and their level of strategic vigilance.

The Importance of the Study

The importance of this study lies in the following:

Theoretical Importance

1. The scarcity of studies addressing intellectual openness in the Sultanate of Oman; therefore, this study will contribute to enriching the field of research related to intellectual openness and to enriching Arab and Omani libraries.

2. The study helps to identify shortcomings in the intellectual openness of school principals, in order to develop plans to address these shortcomings by relevant authorities and decision-makers.

Practical Significance

1. It is hoped that the study's findings will provide researchers with new insights that will contribute to solving some of the problems arising from intellectual stagnation.
2. It can assist stakeholders in establishing the foundations and principles that contribute to fostering intellectual openness, which will positively impact the educational field and the learning process in the Sultanate of Oman.
3. This study opens the door for researchers, graduate students, and those interested in this field to conduct similar studies in the Sultanate of Oman.

Study Limitations

The current study is limited to the following:

1. Subject Matter: The current study examined intellectual openness and its relationship to strategic vigilance among public school principals in the Sultanate of Oman.
2. Population: The study was conducted on a sample of teachers.
3. Geographical Scope: Data was collected from teachers in public schools in three governorates (South Sharqiyah, Al Dakhiliyah, and Muscat) in the Sultanate of Oman.
4. Temporal Scope: The study was conducted during the second semester of the 2025/2026 academic year.

Study Terminology

Intellectual Openness: Al-Salmi, as cited by Al-Anzi (2023), defined it as "awareness, creativity, broad knowledge, and freedom of thought within parameters that distinguish between beneficial and harmful openness, without being dazzled by the culture and thought of others, relying on rational evidence to arrive at sound beliefs and facts" (p. 602).

Operationally, the researcher defines it as: the readiness of public school principals in the Sultanate of Oman to accept new or different ideas and opinions, and to consider them with a critical and balanced mind, without prejudice or preconceived rejection. It is measured by the score recorded by

respondents on the research instrument developed for this study.

Strategic Vigilance: Al-Subaie et al. (2025) defined it as "A continuous process of researching, collecting, processing, and disseminating strategic information for use by decision-makers within the organization to predict future changes in the surrounding environment in order to achieve performance excellence, competitiveness, and sustainability" (p. 425).

The researcher defined it operationally as: the ability of public school principals in the Sultanate of Oman to continuously monitor educational, administrative and societal changes and to be aware of them early in order to make proactive decisions that improve school performance and ensure the continuity of its success, and it is measured by the total score of the study participants' responses on the scale prepared for that purpose.

Method and Procedures

Study Methodology

The current study adopted the descriptive correlational approach, as it is suitable for the nature of the study and its objectives. It seeks to reveal the level of intellectual openness and strategic awareness among the directors of government schools in the Sultanate of Oman, and to identify the nature of the correlational relationship between them, through collecting, analyzing and interpreting data in a scientifically organized manner.

Study Population

The current study population consists of teachers in three governorates (South Al Sharqiyah, Al Dakhiliyah, and Muscat) in the Sultanate of Oman, totaling (52,630) male and female teachers, including (5,467) male and female teachers in the South Al Sharqiyah Governorate, (11,191) male and female teachers in the Muscat Governorate, and (8,972) male and female teachers in the Al Dakhiliyah Governorate for the academic year 2025-2026. (Ministry of Education, 2026).

Study Sample

The current study sample consisted of (380) male and female principals from government schools in the Sultanate of Oman, who were selected using simple random sampling to achieve appropriate representation of the study population.

The sample size was determined based on the Stephen Thompson (2012) formula for determining the optimal sample size in educational studies.

Research Instrument

After reviewing the theoretical literature and previous studies related to the research topic, which addressed intellectual openness and strategic vigilance in educational institutions, the research instrument was developed to align with the objectives of the current study and the nature of its variables. Among the most prominent studies consulted were those by Owaidat (2021) and Al-Subaie et al. (2025), in addition to several theoretical references related to intellectual openness and strategic vigilance. The theoretical and operational concepts and definitions of the variables were also consulted to determine the dimensions of the questionnaire and formulate its items in a precise and scientific manner.

The questionnaire consisted of three parts. The first part included demographic data for the respondents, namely: gender, educational qualification, years of experience, and educational district. The second part addressed the intellectual openness of school principals, comprising 20 items distributed across four dimensions: acceptance of differing opinions, intellectual flexibility, cognitive curiosity, and critical thinking. The third part addressed the strategic vigilance of school principals, consisting of 15 items distributed across three dimensions: environmental vigilance, technological vigilance, and competitive vigilance. A five-point Likert scale was used to answer the questionnaire items, with the following options: strongly agree (5), agree (4), neutral (3), disagree (2), and strongly disagree (1).

Validity and Reliability

First: Face Validity

The questionnaire in its initial form was presented to a group of expert reviewers specializing in educational administration, measurement and evaluation, and educational statistics, with the aim of ensuring the correctness of the linguistic formulation, the clarity of the items, and their suitability to the study's objectives and dimensions. In light of the reviewers' comments, some linguistic modifications were made, and a number of items were reformulated to enhance the instrument's clarity and scientific accuracy.

Second: Item Validity

The questionnaire's validity was verified by calculating

Pearson's correlation coefficients between each item and the total score of the dimension to which it belongs, as well as calculating the correlation coefficient of each dimension with the total score of the domain.

This was done to ensure the internal consistency of the scale items, as shown in Table (1).

Table (1) Pearson's Correlation Coefficient between each item of the Open-Mindedness Scale and the total score of the dimension to which the item belongs.

Part One: Intellectual Openness Scale

First Dimension	Correlation Coefficient	Dimension-to-Domain Correlation	Second Dimension	Correlation Coefficient	Dimension-to-Domain Correlation	Third Dimension	Correlation Coefficient	Dimension-to-Domain Correlation	Fourth Dimension	Correlation Coefficient	Dimension-to-Domain Correlation
Item 1	0.81	**0.93	Item 6	0.79	**0.91	Item 11	0.88	**0.95	Item 16	0.86	**0.94
Item 2	0.84		Item 7	0.76		Item 12	0.85		Item 17	0.89	
Item 3	0.78		Item 8	0.82		Item 13	0.87		Item 18	0.77	
Item 4	0.86		Item 9	0.84		Item 14	0.90		Item 19	0.88	
Item 5	0.83		Item 10	0.80		Item 15	0.89		Item 20	0.91	

(**) Statistically significant at the significance level of (0.01)

Table No. (1) shows that all items of the Intellectual Openness Scale were strongly and statistically significant positively correlated with the dimensions to which they belonged, as the correlation coefficients ranged between (0.76 - 0.91), which are high values indicating good internal consistency between the items and the dimensions of the scale. It also showed that the correlation coefficients of the

dimensions with the total score of the domain were high, as they ranged between (0.91 - 0.95), and all of them are statistically significant at the significance level of (0.01), which indicates that the scale enjoys a high degree of internal validity, and that its items are suitable for measuring what they were designed to measure.

Table No. (2) Pearson's correlation coefficient between each item of the Strategic Vigilance Scale and the total score of the dimension to which the item belongs.

First Dimension	Correlation Coefficient	Dimension-to-Domain Correlation	Second Dimension	Correlation Coefficient	Dimension-to-Domain Correlation	Third Dimension	Correlation Coefficient	Dimension-to-Domain Correlation
Item 21	0.84	**0.94	Item 26	0.88	**0.96	Item 31	0.86	**0.95
Item 22	0.87		Item 27	0.91		Item 32	0.89	
Item 23	0.79		Item 28	0.80		Item 33	0.78	
Item 24	0.90		Item 29	0.89		Item 34	0.92	
Item 25	0.88		Item 30	0.87		Item 35	0.90	

(**) Statistically significant at the significance level of (0.01)

Table (2) shows that all items on the Strategic Vigilance Scale were strongly and statistically significantly positively correlated with their respective dimensions, with correlation coefficients ranging from 0.78 to 0.92. These high values reflect the strong internal consistency of the scale items. The results also demonstrated a high correlation between the dimensions of strategic vigilance and the overall

domain score, with correlation coefficients ranging from 0.94 to 0.96, all statistically significant at the 0.01 level. This indicates the scale's high degree of internal validity and the suitability of its items for field application and achieving the study's objectives.

Scale reliability: In order to verify the scale reliability of the study instrument and its domains, correlation coefficients were calculated between the

study domains on the one hand, and between the study instrument and each other, as shown in Table (3)

Table (3) Values of Cronbach’s alpha coefficients for the intellectual openness axis and the strategic vigilance axis.

Axis	Measurement Domains	Number of Items	Cronbach’s Alpha
Intellectual Openness Axis	Acceptance of Others’ Opinions	1-5	0.89
	Intellectual Flexibility	6-10	0.87
	Cognitive Curiosity	11-15	0.91
	Critical Thinking	16-20	0.90
	Overall Reliability of the Intellectual Openness Axis	20	0.94
Strategic Vigilance Axis	Environmental Vigilance	21-25	0.90
	Technological Vigilance	26-30	0.92
	Competitive Vigilance	31-35	0.89
	Overall Reliability of the Strategic Vigilance Axis	15	0.93
	Overall Reliability of the Study Instrument	35	0.96

The results of Table (3) show that the reliability coefficients for all dimensions and axes of the study were high, with Cronbach's alpha values ranging between (0.87 - 0.92), while the overall reliability coefficient for the intellectual openness axis was (0.94), and for the strategic vigilance axis (0.93), while the overall reliability coefficient for the study instrument was (0.96), which are statistically high values and indicate that the study instrument enjoys a high degree of internal consistency and reliability, which confirms its suitability for field application and the possibility of relying on its results in achieving the study objectives.

Study Procedures

After preparing the study instrument in its initial form, it was presented to a number of specialized referees to verify its scientific validity, then it was applied to a pilot sample to confirm its validity and reliability. After it was approved in its final form, it was applied to the study sample, and then the data was collected, analyzed, and the results were drawn.

Statistical methods used

After collecting the study data, it was entered electronically via Google Forms, then processed and analyzed statistically using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). To verify the reliability and internal consistency of the instrument, Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was used. Pearson's Correlation coefficient was also used to verify the internal consistency and the correlation of items with their dimensions and the overall scale.

Scoring Criteria for the Study Instrument

A five-point Likert scale was used to interpret the study results. To determine response levels, the class width was calculated by finding the range between the highest and lowest values ($5 - 1 = 4$) and then dividing by the number of levels on the scale, resulting in a class width of 0.80. Based on this, the rating levels used to interpret the arithmetic means were determined, as shown in Table (4) concerning the criteria for evaluating the study results.

Table (4) Criteria for judging the interpretation of the results of the study instrument items.

Lower and Upper Limits of the Five-Point Likert Scale

Arithmetic Mean	Level
4.20 – 5.00	Very High
3.40 – 4.19	High
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate
1.80 – 2.59	Low
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low

Results and Discussion

Answer to Question 1

To answer the first question, which stated, "What is the level of intellectual openness among public school principals in the Sultanate of Oman from the teachers' perspective?", the arithmetic means and

standard deviations of the dimensions of intellectual openness and the total score of the scale were used. This was done to determine the level of practice of the dimensions of intellectual openness by school principals and to rank them according to the responses of the study sample, as shown in Table (5).

Table (5) Level of practice of intellectual openness among public school principals in the Sultanate of Oman.

Domain No.	Domain	Rank	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation	Level of Effectiveness
1	Cognitive Curiosity	1	4.45	0.631	Very High
2	Critical Thinking	2	3.96	0.702	High
3	Acceptance of Others' Opinions	3	3.91	0.710	High
4	Intellectual Flexibility	4	3.88	0.644	High
Overall Total	—	—	4.054	0.590	High

The results of the first question showed that the level of intellectual openness practiced by the principals of government schools in the Sultanate of Oman was high, with an overall arithmetic mean of (4.054) and a standard deviation of (0.590). This result is consistent with the study by Hilat (2024) and Malouh and Abdul-Hakim (2022), which also found intellectual openness to be high. This result differed from the findings of the study by Owaidat (2021), which found that the degree of diversity management practiced by private school principals and its relationship to intellectual openness was moderate. This indicates that school principals possess an advanced level of intellectual characteristics related to accepting diverse ideas and opinions, openness to educational innovations, and conscious engagement with contemporary educational issues. The dimension of cognitive curiosity came in first place with an arithmetic mean

of (4.045) and a very high degree, reflecting the interest of school principals in the continuous search for knowledge and keeping up with modern developments in the educational field, which is consistent with the requirements of modern educational leadership based on continuous learning and professional development. Critical thinking came in second place, indicating that administrators tend towards objective analysis of situations and more rational and informed decision-making. Acceptance of differing opinions ranked third, suggesting a good level of educational dialogue and respect for diverse viewpoints within the school environment. Intellectual flexibility, despite receiving a high score, came in last place, which may explain why some administrative practices are still influenced by traditional organizational patterns that can somewhat limit the speed of adaptation to changes and emerging situations. Overall, these

results reflect a positive trend among school administrators towards adopting more open and informed leadership practices, in line with modern trends in educational development in the Sultanate of Oman and the requirements of Oman Vision 2040.

Answer to the second question

To answer the second question, which stated, "What is the level of strategic vigilance among public school

principals in the Sultanate of Oman?" the arithmetic means and standard deviations of the dimensions of strategic vigilance and the total score of the scale were used, with the aim of identifying the level of practice of the dimensions of strategic vigilance by school principals and ranking them according to the responses of the study sample, as shown in Table (6):

Table (6) Level of strategic awareness among public school principals in the Sultanate of Oman.

Domain No.	Domain	Rank	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation	Level of Effectiveness
1	Technological Vigilance	1	4.30	0.623	Very High
2	Competitive Vigilance	2	4.11	0.548	High
3	Environmental Vigilance	3	4.09	0.606	High
Overall Total	—	—	4.170	0.530	High

The results of the second question showed that the level of strategic vigilance among public school principals in the Sultanate of Oman was high, with an overall mean of 4.170 and a standard deviation of 0.530. This result aligns with the study by Lubna and Rateb (2024), which also found a high level of strategic vigilance practiced by school principals. However, this result differed from that of Al-Subaie (2025), which indicated that the level of intellectual vigilance among secondary school principals was moderate. This suggests that school principals possess a high level of strategic awareness and the ability to monitor and proactively address educational and technological changes. The technological vigilance dimension ranked first with a very high mean of 4.301, reflecting the principals' interest in keeping up with technological advancements and integrating them into the school environment. Conversely, the environmental

vigilance dimension ranked last, despite achieving a high score of 4.093, indicating a good level of interest in monitoring environmental and societal changes surrounding the school. The results generally reflect a positive trend among school principals towards adopting modern leadership practices based on foresight, planning and adapting to contemporary changes.

Answer to Question 3

To answer Question 3, which stated, "Is there a statistically significant correlation at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the level of intellectual openness practiced by public school principals in the Sultanate of Oman and their level of strategic vigilance?", Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to reveal the nature of the relationship between intellectual openness and the dimensions of strategic vigilance and its total score, as shown in Table (7).

Table (7) The relationship between intellectual openness and the dimensions of strategic vigilance and its overall degree.

Variable	Correlation Coefficient (r)	Significance Level (Sig.)	Degree of Relationship
Intellectual Openness and Technological Vigilance	0.742	< 0.001	Strong Positive
Intellectual Openness and Competitive Vigilance	0.781	< 0.001	Strong Positive
Intellectual Openness and Environmental Vigilance	0.756	< 0.001	Strong Positive
Intellectual Openness and the Overall Score of Strategic Vigilance	0.814	< 0.001	Strong Positive

The results showed a strong, statistically significant positive correlation ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between intellectual openness and strategic awareness among public school principals in the Sultanate of Oman, with an overall correlation coefficient of 0.814. This high value indicates that higher levels of intellectual openness among school principals are associated with higher levels of strategic awareness. The strongest correlation was found with the dimension of technological awareness, reflecting the link between intellectual openness and the ability of principals to keep abreast of technological developments and address them strategically. This finding underscores the importance of open-mindedness in enhancing the ability of school leaders to anticipate, plan for, and adapt to contemporary educational changes.

Recommendations

In light of the findings of this study on intellectual openness and its relationship to strategic awareness among public school principals in the Sultanate of Oman, the following recommendations can be proposed:

1. Promoting a culture of intellectual openness among public school principals by organizing specialized training programs and workshops that contribute to developing dialogue skills, acceptance of differing opinions, and critical thinking.
2. Integrating intellectual openness and strategic awareness into the professional development programs for school leaders, thereby enhancing their ability to adapt to contemporary educational and technological changes.
3. Encouraging school principals to adopt modern administrative practices based on intellectual flexibility and future foresight in addressing problems and making educational decisions.
4. Providing a school environment that supports dialogue and the exchange of ideas and experiences between teachers and school administration, thereby contributing to fostering intellectual openness and raising the level of strategic awareness within the school.
5. Supporting the use of modern technologies and digital systems in school work, which enhances the technological awareness of school leaders and enables them to effectively keep abreast of educational developments.
- 6- Conducting further studies in the Omani environment that address intellectual openness and its relationship to modern educational variables

such as digital leadership, organizational innovation, decision-making, strategic intelligence, and digital transformation.

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